

Studies on Clay Mineralogy on Forest Soils near Ranchi (Chotanagpur Plateau)

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Manuscript received 16 April 1979, revised 14 August 1980, accepted 29 October 1980

A comparative study of the clay mineralogy of two soil profiles, one from developed and other from under developed forest at Ranchi has been made with a view to ascertain the effects of type of vegetation on the clay mineralogical composition of the soil profile. Kaolinites with fair amounts of illites and chlorites are the dominant clay minerals in both the cases. No significant variation in the mineralogical make up of the profiles developed under the different forest conditions could be observed excepting slight changes at the lower depth in the profile developed under the tree forest condition.

VEGETATION in Chotanagpur according to Champion's Forest types is Dry Peninsular Sal consisting of different types of deciduous trees. However, two distinct forest developments could be noticed—one is underdeveloped scrub forest consisting mainly of shrubby, herbaceous and spreading grass species with few trees. The other one is a developed forest—the sub-tropical sal forest—with a dominant species of *Shorea robusta* which is considered to be a post climax formations. These forests often grow close together on red-yellow-light grey catenary soils group of Ranchi developed on Archean gneiss.

Mitchell¹ noted that vegetation is one among various environmental factors which has important effect in the genesis of clay minerals. Keeping this in mind and in view of inadequate knowledge available on the clay mineralogy on forest soils, an attempt has been made in the present communication to study two typical profiles—one each from developed and underdeveloped forest—to see the changes, if any, in the clay mineralogy as a result of soil profile development on varying vegetations between them.

Experimental

The chemical composition of the clay fraction < 0.002 mm freed from soluble SiO_2 and free R_2O_3 by Na_2S and oxalic acid² was determined with the methods referred by Jackson³.

The C.E.C. was determined with BaCl_2 -triethanolamine buffered to pH 8.2 (method of Mehlich⁴). The organic matter was destroyed by repeated treatments of 10% H_2O_2 and the iron oxides were removed with sodium hydrosulphite and sodium citrate at pH 7.3 according to Aguilera and

Jackson⁵. The clay fraction was sampled at a depth of 10 cm from the surface after 8 hours.

T.G.A. were made after the methods of Kelley, Woodford, Dore and Brown⁶. 1 g of the sample was heated to constant weight at 100°, 150° and at 100° intervals throughout the temperature range between 200 to 800°. The weight at 800° was taken as the base weight.

Linseis apparatus was used for D.T.A. The rate of heating was 10°/minute. The thermocouple was Pt/Pt-Rh, 0.5 g of powdered sample were analysed. The inert sample was calcinated Kaolin.

Philips diffractometer was used for the X-ray diffraction analyses of the clay fraction. Diffractions were made with copper K α radiation rendered monochromatic with nickel filters.

TABLE 1 -CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE CLAY FRACTION <0.002 mm FREED FROM SOLUBLE SILICA AND FREE SESQUIOXIDES

Horizon	SiO_2 %	Fe_2O_3 %	Al_2O_3 %	TiO_2 %	K_2O %	$\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ molar ratio
<i>Profile 1</i>						
A ₂	32.06	8.14	28.40	1.11	1.25	1.92
B ₁	36.27	9.42	28.60	0.92	1.26	2.09
B _{2-1t}	39.31	9.58	28.92	1.11	1.26	2.31
B _{2-2t}	49.34	10.52	27.98	1.01	1.24	2.99
<i>Profile 2</i>						
A ₂	33.03	9.66	28.48	0.95	1.33	1.97
B ₁	38.11	9.90	29.36	0.99	1.44	2.21
B _{2-1t}	49.27	9.90	30.95	1.01	0.59	2.72
B _{2-2t}	51.46	9.86	28.95	1.12	0.71	3.02

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TABLE 2—CATION EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF DIFFERENTLY TREATED FINE EARTH (<2 mm) AND CLAY FRACTION (<0.002 mm)

Horizon	C.E.C. of un- treated fine earth	C.E.C. of fine earth without organic matter	Organic Carbon of fine earth	C.E.C. of fine earth without organic matter and without Fe ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃ removed from fine earth	C.E.C. of the clay fraction without organic matter and with Fe ₂ O ₃
	meg/100 g	meg/100 g	%	meg/100 g	%	meg/100 g
<i>Profile 1</i>						
A ₁	9.00	8.85	0.22	10.10	1.21	19
B ₁	15.95	15.11	0.27	16.10	1.29	20
B _{2-1t}	19.57	18.92	0.18	19.92	1.89	26
B _{2-2t}	17.70	16.99	0.26	18.50	1.89	23
<i>Profile 2</i>						
A ₂	8.75	8.10	0.29	9.40	1.54	20
B ₁	13.85	12.98	0.27	14.20	1.66	24
B _{2-1t}	14.70	11.92	0.22	12.10	2.50	32
B _{1-2t}	14.30	11.23	0.19	12.68	2.60	33

Results and Discussion

The chemical composition of the clay fraction <0.002 mm freed from soluble silica and free sesquioxides is given in Table 1. The two profiles show similar changes in the chemical composition of the clay fraction. This is best illustrated by the SiO₂/Al₂O₃ ratio which increases down the profiles. The values indicate both 1:1 and 2:1 lattic minerals. The low K₂O content in B_{2-1t} and B_{2-2t} horizons of profile 2 corresponds to the formation of montmorillonite according to Grim⁷ (confirmed by X-ray diffraction). Prasad *et al*⁸ analysed clay fraction of surface soils of Ranchi and reported SiO₂/Al₂O₃ molar ratios between 1.17-2.81.

Table 2 represents the C.E.C. of differently treated fine earth and of the clay fraction. Destruction of the organic matter reduces slightly the cation exchange capacity in all the horizons of the profiles. However, the reduction is significant in B_{2-1t} and B_{2-2t} of profile 2. This suggests different compositions of the exchange material. The removal of oxide coating from soils has long been found necessary. Fe₂O₃ removed by sodium hydrosulphite and sodium citrate at pH 7.3 increases the C.E.C. in all horizons. According to Aguilera and Jackson⁵, any method employed for the removal of iron oxides will have some destructive effect on layer silicate colloids; with consequent loss or gain in cation exchange capacity. Biswas *et al*⁹ reported for the soil clays which are dominantly illitic, the removal of iron oxides resulted in higher C.E.C. of the clay fraction whereas in soil clays dominant in montmorillonites such a removal had the opposite effect i.e., lowering in C.E.C. of the soil clays.

The C.E.C. values indicate the presence of kaolinites, illites and chlorite. The D.T.A. curves and X-ray diffraction pattern (See later on) confirm the presence of these minerals. X-ray diffraction

Fig. 1. Loss of weight of the clay fraction <0.002 mm of Profile 1 with increase of temperature from 100° to 800° (weight at 800° is the base weight).

also indicate the presence of little montmorillonite and vermiculite in the B_{2-1t} and B_{2-2t} horizons of profile 2.

The loss of weight of the clay fraction with increase of temperature is given in Figs. 1 and 2. All the samples show a slight loss of weight above 600°. The total loss is indicated between 8.5 to 26.5%. The curves suggest a mixture of kaolinites (loss between 400-600°) and illites and chlorite (loss between 300-500°) in all horizons of the profiles. According to Ross and Kerr¹⁰ most of the dehydration of the kaolinites takes place between about 400 and 525°. Dehydration curves for illites published by Grim, Bray and Bradley¹¹ show a relatively large loss from 300 to about 500° and a gradual loss above 500°. Nutting¹² presented dehydration curves for several chlorites which show maximum loss around 550°.

Fig. 2. Loss of weight of the clay fraction <0.002 mm of Profile 2 with increase of temperature from 100° to 800° (weight at 800° is the base weight).

The D.T.A. curves are given in Figs. 3-4. The nature of the thermograms is more or less similar in all horizons of the two profiles. They all gave endothermic reactions at 100-200° and at 550-650° and exothermic reactions at 250-450° and at 880-1030°. The endothermic reaction at 550-650° indicates kaolinites or illites. The endothermic reaction at 100-200° is indicative of illites or

Fig. 3. D.T.A. Curves of the clay fraction <0.002 mm of Profile 1.

Fig. 4. D.T.A. Curves of the clay fraction <0.002 mm of Profile 2.

montmorillonites or vermiculite^{13,14}. B₁, B_{2-1t} and B_{2-2t} of profile 2 exhibit large endothermic peaks around 180°. This may indicate the presence of montmorillonites and vermiculite. X-ray diffraction pattern, however, confirms the presence of these minerals in B_{2-1t} and B_{2-2t} horizons. The exothermic reactions at 880-1030° indicate a mixture of kaolinites and montmorillonites^{7,15}. The exothermic reactions at 250-350° are due to chelated oxalates of iron and aluminium formed during oxidation of organic matter with H₂O₂.

The D.T.A. curves thus suggest that dominant clay minerals are kaolinites and illites in all horizons of the two profiles. Little montmorillonites and vermiculite indicated by D.T.A. in B_{2-1t} and B_{2-2t} horizons of profile 2 are confirmed by X-ray diffraction. Our findings are in well agreement with the earlier work done by Sinha and Mandal⁸ who reported, that red loam soil clays of Chotanagpur contained kaolinite and illite as dominant clay minerals with occasional occurrence of chlorite.

The X-ray diffraction patterns (Tables 3 and 4) show the essential peaks of minerals present in

TABLE 3—X-RAY DIFFRACTION PATTERN OF THE CLAY FRACTION 0.002 mm

d(Å)	Inten- sity	d(Å)	Inten- sity	d(Å)	Inten- sity	d(Å)	Inten- sity
Profile 1 A ₂		B ₁		B _{2.1t}		B _{2.2t}	
		14.24	w	14.24	w	14.24	w
10.10	w	10.10	w	10.10	m	10.10	m
7.07	s	7.07	s	7.07	m	7.07	m
—	—	4.71	w	4.71	w	4.71	w
4.48	w	4.48	w	4.48	m	4.48	m
4.26	m	4.26	w	4.26	w	4.26	w
3.55	s	3.55	s	3.55	m	3.53	m
3.34	w	3.34	s	3.34	w	3.34	w
Profile 2 A ₂		B ₁		B _{2.1t}		B _{2.2t}	
14.24	w	14.24	w	14.24	m	14.24	m
10.10	w	10.10	m	10.10	s	10.10	s
7.07	s	7.07	m	7.07	m	7.07	m
4.71	w	4.71	w	4.71	m	4.71	m
4.48	w	4.48	m	4.48	s	4.48	m
4.26	w	4.26	w	4.26	w	4.26	w
3.55	s	3.53	m	3.53	m	3.53	m
3.34	m	3.34	w	3.34	w	3.34	w

s=strong, m=medium, w=weak

in all samples except in A₂ of profile 1. 3.34 Å line is characteristic of quartz. 4.26 Å line is indicative of other kaolinite group mineral. Our findings are well comparable with those of Prasad *et al*⁸ who reported from X-ray diffractions the dominance of kaolinites with fair amounts of illites and small amounts of chlorite like minerals and montmorillonites in some sedentary soils of Bihar.

X-ray diffraction patterns thus show the presence of kaolinites, illites in all horizons of the two profiles, chlorite present in all samples except in A₂ of Profile 1, and small amounts of montmorillonite and vermiculite in B_{2.1t} and B_{2.2t} horizons of Profile 2.

B_{2.2t}

B_{2.1t}

Heated The Samples For 500°C For 24 Hours

B_{2.2t}

B_{2.1t}

Fig. 5. Ethylene Glycol Treated Samples.

TABLE 4—X-RAY DIFFRACTION PATTERN OF THE HEATED AND ETHYLENE GLYCOL TREATED CLAY FRACTIONS <0.002 mm

Horizon	Heated to 500° for 24 hours	Heated to 600° for 1 hour	Ethylene glycol treated	
	New peak at 10Å	Reflection at 7.07Å	14.24A	16.17A
Profile 1				
A ₂	—	Disappeared	—	—
B ₁	—	Do	Appeared	—
B _{2.1t}	—	Do	Do	—
B _{2.2t}	—	Do	Do	—
Profile 2				
A ₂	—	Do	Appeared	—
B ₁	—	Do	Do	—
B _{2.1t}	Appeared	Do	Do	Appeared
B _{2.2t}	Do	Do	Do	Do

different horizons of soil profiles studied. The 7.07 and 3.55 Å lines present in all samples are indicative of kaolinites present. The 7.07 Å line when heated to 600° for one hour disappeared in the case of all horizons confirming the presence of kaolinites. The 10-10 and 4.48 Å lines present in all samples are indicative of the presence of illites. The 14-24 Å line present in samples remaining after heat treatment to 600° indicates chlorite like minerals. The 14-24 Å line shifted to the region of 17 Å after the ethylene glycol treatment in B_{2.1t} and B_{2.2t} of profile 2 indicating the presence of montmorillonites⁷ in these horizons. Again, B_{2.1t} and B_{2.2t} of profile 2 show new lines in the region of 10 Å after the samples are heated to 500° for 24 hours which indicate vermiculite⁷ in some quantities. The 4.71 Å line is characteristic of chlorite present

DESCRIPTION OF PROFILES

Profile 1

Location :	Ormanjhi, Ranchi.
Exposure :	Slope 2-3%
Land Form :	Upland Virgin, slightly rolling relief, well drained, severe erosion.
Vegetation :	<i>Lantana camara</i> , <i>Gossypium</i> sp., <i>Argostis</i> sp. Underdeveloped scrub forest consisting mainly of shrubby, herbaceous and spreading grass species with few trees.
Horizon :	A ₂ 0-27 cm Red yellow (D 5 YR 6/6) to yellowish red (M 5 YR 5/6); Loamy sand; weak fine granular to subangular; friable when moist and soft when dry; abundant fine and few medium roots; abrupt and smooth boundary.

TABLE 5—INFERENCE FROM DIFFERENT EXPERIMENTS MADE ON CLAY FRACTION <0.002 mm

Horizon	Chemical composition data	C.E.C. data	Thermogravimetric analysis	D.T.A. curves	X-ray diffraction pattern
<i>Profile 1</i>					
A ₂	2 : 1 & 1 : 1 Lattice mineral	Kaolinites Illites and Chlorite	Kaolinites Illites and Chlorite	Kaolinites and Illites	Kaolinites (S) Illites (W)
B ₁	Do	Do	Do	Do	Kaolinites (S) Illites (W) Chlorite (W)
B _{2,1t}	Do	Do	Kaolinites Mica type minerals and Chlorite	Do	Kaolinites (m) Illites (m) Chlorite (W)
B _{2,2t}	Do	Do	Kaolinites Illites and Chlorite	Do	Kaolinites (m) Illites (m) Chlorite (W)
<i>Profile 2</i>					
A ₂	2 : 1 and 1 : 1 Lattice mineral	Kaolinites Illites and Chlorite	Kaolinites Illites and Chlorite	Kaolinites and Illites	Kaolinites (S) Illites (W) Chlorite (W)
B ₁	Do	Do	Do	Do	Kaolinites (m) Illites (m) Chlorite (W)
B _{2,1t}	Do	Do	Do	Do+indications of Montmorillonites and Vermiculite	Kaolinites (m) Illites (S) Chlorite (m) Montmorillonites (W) Vermiculite (W)
B _{2,2t}	Do	Do	Do	Do+Do	Do

B₁ 27-70 cm Red yellow (D 5 YR 6/8) to yellowish red (M 5 YR 4/6), sandy loam to loam; moderate medium subangular blocky; friable when moist and slightly hard when dry; many fine and few medium roots, gradual and smooth boundary.

B_{2,1t} 70-97 cm Yellowish red (D 5 YR 5/6) to red (M 2.5 YR 4/6), loam; moderate medium subangular blocky, firm when moist and hard when dry, few medium roots, clear and wavy boundary.

B_{2,2t} 97-130 cm Yellowish red (D 5 YR 5/8) to red (M 2.5 YR 5/8), loam; moderate medium angular blocky; firm when moist and dry when hard, few fine distinct mottles; clear and wavy boundary.

B₁ 25-44 cm Yellowish red (D 5 YR 5/8) to yellowish red (M 5 YR 4/6); clay loam medium moderate subangular blocky; firm when moist and hard when dry; many fine and few medium roots; clear and smooth boundary.

B_{2,1t} 44.64 cm Red (D 2.5 YR 5/8) to dark red (M 2.5 YR 3/6); clay loam; medium moderate angular blocky firm when moist and hard when dry; few fine roots; clear and wavy boundary.

B_{2,2t} 65-105 cm Storing brown (D 7.5 YR 5/6) to yellow red (M 5 YR 5/6); sandy clay loam medium to coarse angular blocky; firm when moist and hard when dry; few fine roots; gradual and smooth boundary.

Profile 2

Land Form : Upland, plain and virgin, normal relief, well drained, no erosion.

Vegetation : *Shorea robusta*, *Syzygium cumini*, *Madhuca indica*. Developed subtropical sal forest.

Horizon : A₂ 0-25 cm Reddish yellow (D 5 YR 6/6) to yellowish red (M 5 YR 5/6); Sandy clay loam; medium moderate angular blocky; friable when moist and slightly hard when dry; many fine and medium roots; abrupt and smooth boundary.

Regarding the mineralogical composition between the two profiles studied, the experiments show (See inferences from different experiments, Table 5) that the dominating clay minerals are kaolinites, illites and chlorite in all the horizons of the two profiles.

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